

Globalisation and its Effects on Service Sector in India

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Abstract	The impact of globalization on Indian industries started when the Government opened the markets of the country to foreign investments in the early 1990s. The service sector has played a pivotal role in the acceleration of economic growth. The growth picked up in the 1980's and accelerated in the 1990's. Since then, it has become a dominant contributor to economic growth.
Keywords	Service Sector, Globalisation, Acceleration, Investment, Pivotal etc
Introduction	Conventional wisdom suggests that during the early development phase of any country, expansion of output in manufactured goods precedes growth in the service sector. As a country progresses further, manufacturing often takes on back seat, giving way to the service sector in terms of both output and employment, and manufacturing firms themselves become increasingly service centric in order to remain competitive. In India's case, there are positive spillovers from services growth to manufacturing, through income, demand, technology, and organisational learning. The service sector covers a wide range of activities from the most sophisticated information technology (IT) to simple services provided by the unorganized sector, such as the services of the barber and plumber. National Accounts classification of the service sector incorporates trade, hotels and restaurants, transport, storage and communication, financing, insurance, real estate and business services and community, social and personal services, construction etc.
Objective of study	The paper intends to make an analysis of the different services sectors in India and the effects of globalization on them. Globalisation has attracted the industries in India and service sectors are no exception to it.
Review of Literature	Globalisation implies a comprehensive and self-evident process working towards establishing a worldwide aggregative whole of an economic structure into which all economies of the world must integrate today or tomorrow. This includes services which in most economies are the single largest contributor to economic growth and employment. Global importance of service sector in terms of their share in national income/GDP has attracted the attention of the economists all over the world. To justify the growing importance of the tertiary sector in the recent period, the factors mentioned above have the increasing role of the government in implementing the objectives of growth, employment generation and poverty alleviation, the historical role of the urban middle class in wholesale trade and distribution and the demonstration effect in developing countries creating demand patterns similar to those of developed countries (Panchmukhi, Numbia, and Mehta, 1996). The increase in demand for services emphasizes the role of increasing connections between manufacturing and services and transfer of service-type activities outside the firm (Fuchs, 1968), Kutcher and Personick 1986, Tschatter, 1987, Barker, 1990. Moreover, income growth increases the market for services and expands the size of service sector, which benefits the industrial sector in two ways-first, by enabling greater specialization and division of labour, and second, by covering the effective costs of service inputs to industrial production (Jones and Kierzkowski, 1988; Francosis, 1990). Greater varieties of competing services afford greater flexibility to producer in minimizing the cost of producing a given level of output. If there were no fixed costs in producing services, however, there would be an infinite variety available in the market, because each firm in the industrial sector would demand an infinitely small amount of an infinite variety of services. But as long as there are fixed costs, the extent of variety will be limited by the size of the market for services. This gives a link between income growth and the efficiency of industrial production (Eswaran & Kotwal, 2002). The expansion of government sector has a casual relationship with development in either agriculture or industry (Mitra, 1988).
Methodology	To study the growth of service sector in Indian economy, study of pre-globalisation Indian economy has been made. After globalization, Government of India opened up the certain market to the private sector. So, the secondary data relating to the macro economic variables, like: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Growth in the number of companies and the size of the operation. 2. Increase in the investment in these sectors. 3. Their investments in other countries. 4. The growth in the production, consumption and exports. 5. Increase in the import of technology.

6. The foreign exchange earnings.

The linkage effect for the growth of Indian economy and other vital information were collected for two different periods like pre and post globalization era, and the changes in the growth and other related parameters were also studied.

The study is based on secondary data collected from various sources. Some of the data have been collected from Business Magazines, various official websites of India and from annual reports of different companies in various sectors. Apart from this, information is also tapped from journals, magazines, daily newspapers like Capital market, Economic Times, The Telegraph, The Business Line, The Hindu, Financial Express etc.

Role of Service Sectors in Indian Economy

India ranks 13th position in services output. The services sector provides employment to 23% of the work force and is growing quickly, with a growth rate of 80% in 2001-2011, from 4.5% in 1951-81. It has the largest share in the GDP, accounting for 60% in 2011, up from 15% in 1951. India depends on service sector heavily for around 60% of its GDP and growth. It is also a significant employment generator. Service sector encompasses a variety like tourism, rail freight, logistics, hotel industry, health care, financial services like insurance and banking that have been growing at 28% over the last 5 years, which is remarkably higher than the GDP growth of 7%. India is one of the fastest growing retail market in the world, with 1.30 billion people.

The sectoral disaggregation of national income shows that the service sector has been growing relatively faster than other two sectors-primary and secondary throughout the post-independence period of the Indian economy. The economy has successfully navigated the turbulent years of the recent global economic crisis because of the vitality of this sector in the domestic economy and its prominent role in India's external economic interactions. This sector plays a leading role in the economy of India. In the current economic scenario, it looks that the boom in the services sector in India is fast emerging as global services hub.

Table-1
Performance of India's Service Sector: Some Indicators

Sector	Indicators	Unit & Period, 2011-12
Aviation	Airline Passenger (Domestic and International)	59.3 millions
Telecom	Telecom medications (wireline and wireless)	9265.3 lakh
Tourism	Foreign exchange earnings from tourist arrivals	6.29 million
Shipping	Gross tonnage of Indian shipping (No. of ships)	11.06 million tons
Ports	Port traffic	488.8 million tons
Railway	Freight traffic by railways	704.4 millions tons
Storage	Storage capacity No. of warehouses	99.81 mt.

Source : Economic survey report, 2011-12

Growth of different services

The growth of different services in India may be summarized as follows:

Trade

Trade is an important activity providing interface between the producer and consumer. The value of trade inclusive of wholesale and retail in the organized and unorganized sectors in India's GDP at constant prices has grown at a CAGR of 10 percent. The share of trade in GDP has been slightly above 15 percent in the last six years. Retail industry is one of the pillars of Indian economy and accounts for 15% of the G.D.P. with a high GDP growth in the last 5 years, and high growth in consuming population, the retail business is of late being hailed as one of the sunrise sectors in the economy. Since 2006, India has been allowing FDI in single brand retail to the extent of 51 percent. Recently, India opened its super harvest sector to foreign chains. The Government has decided to allow foreign airlines to buy stakes of upto 49 percent in local carriers.

Tourism including hotels and restaurants

Tourism is not only a growth engine but also an export growth engine and employment generator. It produces more than 7% of the world's total jobs directly and millions more indirectly through the multiplier effect as per the U.N World Tourism Organization. Since tourism does not fall under single heading in India's National Accounts Statistics, its contribution has to be estimated. Its contribution to GDP and employment in 2011 was 6.0 and 10.00 percent respectively. In India, the tourism sector has witnessed significant growth in recent years.

Real Estate Service

The real estate industry has significant linkages (both direct and indirect) with nearly 3000 sectors like cement, steel, paints and building hardware which not only contribute to capital formation and generation of employment and income opportunities, but also catalyse and stimulate economic growth. Therefore, investment in housing and the GDP share of the real estate sector (including ownership of dwellings) along with business services was 10.6 percent in 2011. Generally, about 5 percent of India's GDP is contributed by the housing sector. While India is among the top countries in terms of the housing and work space needs, it ranks 181 position in construction permission processes according to the World Bank report.

Transport Related Services

Shipping

Shipping is an important indicator of both commodity and services trade of any country. It plays an important role in the Indian economy with around 95 percent of the country's trade by volume and 68 percent in terms of value being transported by sea. India had a

fleet strength of 1,122 ships with gross tonnage of 6,122 ships. With gross tonnage of 11.06 million, the public sector shipping corporation of India having the largest share of 36.17 percent of this, 372 ships with 10.01 million GT later to India's overseas trade and the rest to coastal trade.

Port Services

Ports are the vital link in the trade between nations. Continuous modernization of ports and upgradation of port infrastructure is important to increase the productivity and efficiency of ports. The total capacity of Indian ports has reached approximately 1,260 million tonnes in 2018-19. The biggest public-private partnership (PPP) project in the port sector has been awarded in the JNPT, Mumbai.

Storage Services

Warehousing services are an integral part of both in-bound and out-bound logistics, as goods produced have to be stored in different geographical locations before shipping/dispatch as per demand. order flows. In India the most important component of warehousing is agricultural storage for agri-produce, food grains, fertilizers, manure, etc. Other components include industrial goods, import cargo and exercisable cargo, inland container depots, container freight station for facilitating import/export trade and special warehouses for cold and temperature controlled storage.

Banking Industry

The Indian money market is classified into the organized sector, comprising private, public and foreign owned commercial banks, and cooperative banks, together known as scheduled banks, and the unorganized sector which includes individual or family owned indigenous bankers or moneylenders and non-banking financial companies. The Indian Banking system has successfully passed through the various phase of reforms and has also faced the stress posed by the global financial turmoil in the recent past. There are some important reforms such as the deregulation of interest rates on Saving Bank deposits and NRE deposits.

Software Industry

The Software Industry employs more than 3 lakh employees. The Indian Software Industry is largely complementary to the China industry. Indian firms provide essential maintenance and development services, enabling US and China firms to use their scarce in house IT staff for higher value added work, such as design and develop new types of applications. In doing so, Indian firms often act as subcontractors to establish China and other developed nations like U.S. software services, firms and systems integrators, In addition, many of these firms rely on Indian programmers and have significant India based operations. Many firms are likely to increase their business involvement in India.

Accounting and Auditing services

Indian accounting firms are increasingly getting integrated and are providing associated services, such as management consultancy, corporate finance, and advisory services in addition to their core business of accounting, auditing and tax services.

R & D Services

The sectors which attracted largest R & D expenditure were pharmaceuticals, electrical and non-electrical machinery, transport equipment, electronics and plastics, R & D intensity for the pharmaceuticals sector was much higher than that for other sectors.

Telecom Services

Indian telecom has proved to be an international success story with the sector witnessing commendable growth over the past few years. The Indian telecom network is ranked as the second largest in the world only next to China. The growth in wireless connections has been phenomenal, taking their share to over 96 percent of total telephones in the country.

Posts

Indian Post has the largest postal network in the world with 1.60 lakh post offices across the length and breadth of the country. On the average, each post office serves 8000 persons with coverage of approx. 22 sq. km. The largest number of post offices are located in rural areas.

Health Care Industry

India spends about 7% of GDP on Health Care. Out of this, 2% is in the Government sector and 5% in private sector. Provision of health Care in the country is the shared responsibility of the centre, state and local Government. It includes beneficiaries covered under ESIS, CGHs, Army, Railways, Self-funded, PSWS and Insurance products. Most of the health care providers in the country are in private sector and are on fee for service basis. The share of public financing in total health care is just about 1% of GDP compared to 2.8% in other developed countries.

Legal Services

India has an estimated 60 lakh legal practitioners and is next only to the USA in terms of numbers. The service providers are individual lawyers and small or family based firms. In India, the practice of law is governed by the Advocates Act of 1961. Under this act, foreign law firms are not allowed to engage in practice of law in India. Many foreign legal firms have set-up liaison offices, while a few have established referral relationships with Indian firms. India is ranked 51st with a score of 4.3 in terms of judicial independence by the global competitiveness report 2011-12.

Consultancy Services

Consultancy Services are emerging as one of the main business areas in India. The nature of revenue in the Indian consulting industry on conservative basis has been estimated at around US \$ 8.24 billion and presently, it contributes to about 5% of the GDP. The growth rates of the industry over the last few years have been extremely

promising and revenue is projected to increase to U.S \$ 9.89 billion by 2012 at a growth rate of 20 percent.

Conclusion

Growth has mainly been driven by increasing specialization of production, rising living standard and accelerated urbanization. There are also some non-economic factors which are difficult to be quantified but have played definite roles in services development in India. India's service sector is now the dominant contributory to GDP growth, but employment absorption is not very high in this sector. India needs industrialization even more as millions of rural workers have to be employed and the IT sector is not large enough to significantly affect the growth of the national economy.

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